

Publications based on work at the TGB Osborn Vegetation Reserve

Journal articles

- Andrew, M.H. and Lange, R.T. (1986) The spatial distributions of sympatric populations of kangaroos and sheep: Examples of dissociation between these species. *Aust. Wildl. Res.* 13: 367-373.
- Boland, J. and Sinclair, R. (2014) Developing age-size relationships for long lived tree species. *Journal of Biological Systems* 22: 309-326.
- Bowman AS, Facelli JM, Sinclair R (2015) Long-term influence of fallen logs on patch formation and their effects under contrasting grazing regimes. *Austral Ecology* 40, 238–244.
- Carrodus, B.B. and Specht, R.L. (1965) Factors affecting the relative distribution of *Atriplex vesicaria* and *Kochia sedifolia* (Chenopodiaceae) in the arid zone of South Australia. *Aust. J. Bot.* 13: 419-433.
- Carrodus, B.B., Specht, R.L. and Jackman, M.L. (1965) The vegetation of Koonamore Station, South Australia. *Trans. Roy. Soc. S. Aust.* 89: 41-57.
- Cox, J.A. and Conran, J.G. (1996) The effect of water stress on the life cycles of *Erodium crinitum* Carolin and *Erodium cicutarium* (L.) L'Hérit. Ex Aiton (Geraniaceae) *Australian Journal of Ecology* 21, 235 - 240.
- Crisp, M.D. (1978) Demography and survival under grazing of three semi-desert shrubs. *Oikos* 30: 520-528.
- Crisp, M.D. and Lange, R.T. (1976) Age structure, distribution and survival under grazing of the arid-zone shrub *Acacia burkittii*. *Oikos*: 27: 86-92.
- Emmerson, L. M. and Facelli, J. M. (1996) Bluebush mound heights - an indicator of grazing regime? in Conference Papers, The Australian Rangeland Society 9th Biennial Conference, eds L.P. Hunt and R. Sinclair. Australian Rangeland Society, Port Augusta, South Australia, pp227-228.
- Emmerson, L.M., Facelli, J. M. and Chesson, P.L. (1996) The effect of grazing on local populations of *Erodiohyllum elderi*. in Conference Papers, The Australian Rangeland Society 9th Biennial Conference, eds L.P. Hunt and R. Sinclair. Australian Rangeland Society, Port Augusta, South Australia, pp229-230.
- Fatchen, T.J. (1978) Change in grazed *Atriplex vesicaria* and *Kochia astrotricha* (Chenopodiaceae) populations, 1929-1974. *Transactions of the Royal Society of South Australia* 102: 39-42.
- Green, G.M. (1986) Use of SIR-A and Landsat MSS data in mapping shrub and inter-shrub vegetation at Koonamore, South Australia. *Photogram. Eng. & Remote Sensing* 52: 659~70.
- Greenslade, P.J.M. (1975) The role of soil fauna in arid shrubland in South Australia. In *Progress in Zoology; Proceedings of the 5th International Colloquium on Soil Zoology, Prague 1973*. Academia, Publishing house of the Czechoslovak Academy of Sciences. pp113-119.
- Greenslade, Penelope (1992) Conserving invertebrate diversity in agricultural, forestry and natural ecosystems in Australia. *Agriculture, Ecosystems and Environment* 40: 297-312.
- Greenslade, Penelope. (1981) Survival of Collembola in arid environments: observations in South Australia and the Sudan. *Journal of Arid Environments*. 4(3), 219-228.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-1963\(18\)31563-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0140-1963(18)31563-5)
- Greenslade, P.J. M. and Greenslade, Penelope (1973) Ants of a site in arid southern Australia. *Proceedings of the VII Congress of the IUSI, London*. pp 145-149.
- Greenslade, P.J. M. and Greenslade, Penelope (1984) Soil surface insects of the Australian arid zone. In *Arid Australia*, eds H.G. Cogger and E.E. Cameron, Australian Museum, Sydney. pp 153-176.
- Hall, E.A.A., Specht, R.L. and Eardley, C.M. (1964) Regeneration of the vegetation on Koonamore Vegetation Reserve, 1926 - 1962. *Aust. J. Bot.* 12: 205-264.
- Hastwell, G.T. and Facelli, J.M. (2003) Differing effects of shade-induced facilitation on growth and survival during the establishment of a chenopod shrub. *Journal of Ecology* 91: 941-950.
- Lawley, V., Parrot, L., Lewis, M., Sinclair, R. and Ostendorf, B. (2013) Self-organization and complex dynamics of regenerating vegetation in an arid ecosystem: 82 years of recovery after grazing. *Journal of Arid Environments* 88: 156-164.

Publications based on work at the TGB Osborn Vegetation Reserve

- Long, X., Guan, H., Sinclair, R., Batelaan, O., Facelli, J.M., Andrew, R.L., Bestland, E. (2018) Response of vegetation cover to climate variability in protected and grazed arid rangelands of South Australia. *Journal of Arid Environments* 161, 64–71. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jaridenv.2018.10.001>
- McArthur, L., Boland, J. and Tiver, F. (2006) A model to detect grazing sensitivity of *Myoporum platycarpum* in the arid rangelands of South Australia. *Natural Resource Modelling* 19: 587-607.
- Noble, I.R. (1977) Long-term biomass dynamics in an arid chenopod shrub community at Koonamore, South Australia. *Aust. J. Bot.* 25: 639-653.
- Noble, I.R. (1986) The Dynamics of Range Ecosystems. In "Rangelands, a Resource under Siege." Proc. 2nd Internat. Rangelands Congress. Aust. Acad. Science, Canberra, pp3-5.
- Noble, I.R. and Crisp, M.D. (1980) Germination and growth models of short-lived grass and forb populations based on long term photo-point data at Koonamore, South Australia. *Israel J. Bot.* 28: 195-210.
- Osborn, T.G.B. (1925a) On the ecology of the vegetation of arid Australia. No.1. Introduction and general description of the Koonamore Reserve for the study of the saltbush flora. *Trans. Roy. Soc. S. Aust.* 49: 290-297.
- Osborn, T.G.B. (1925b) The fodder plants of arid Australia. *The Pastoral Review*, Nov.16, 1925.
- Osborn, T.G.B. (1926a) Methods of work in semi-arid and arid Australia. In "Aims and Methods in the Study of Vegetation". eds AG Tansley and TF Chipp British Empire Vegetation Committee and Crown Agents for the Colonies, Ch 13; 269-273.
- Osborn, T.G.B. (1926b) The factors influencing the regeneration of vegetation in the arid parts of Australia, with special reference to the pastoral industry. *Rept. Aust. Assn. Adv. Science* 18: 823-824.
- Osborn, T.G.B. (1927-28) The Koonamore Vegetation Reserve. *CSIR Journal* 1: 365-368.
- Osborn, T.G.B. (1931) Report to University of Adelaide Council on the Koonamore Vegetation Reserve. University of Adelaide Archives Series 150. Reports to Council, for 1931.
- Osborn, T.G.B. and Wood, J.G. (1923) On some halophytic and non-halophytic plant communities in arid South Australia. *Transactions and Proceedings of the Royal Society of South Australia* 47: 388-399
- Osborn, T.G.B., Wood, J.G. and Paltridge, T.B. (1931) On the autecology of *Stipa nitida*, a study of a fodder grass in arid Australia. *Proc. Linn. Soc. NSW.* 56: 299-324.
- Osborn, T.G.B., Wood, J.G. and Paltridge, T.B. (1932) On the growth and reaction to grazing of the perennial saltbush, *Atriplex vesicarium*. An ecological study of the biotic factor. *Proc. Linn. Soc. NSW* 57: 377-402.
- Osborn, T.G.B., Wood, J.G. and Paltridge, T.B. (1935) On the climate and vegetation of the Koonamore Vegetation Reserve to 1931. *Proc. Linn. Soc. NSW.* 60: 392-427.
- Rogers, R.W. (1974) Lichens from the T.G.B. Osborn Vegetation Reserve at Koonamore in arid South Australia. *Trans. Roy. Soc. S. Aust.* 98: 113-124.
- Silander, J.A. (1983) Demographic variation in the Australian desert cassia under grazing pressure. *Oecologia* 60: 227-233.
- Sinclair, R. (1984) The T.G.B. Osborn Reserve; Koonamore. *Aust. Rangel. Soc., Range Management Newsletter* 84/4.
- Sinclair, R. (1986) The T.G.B. Osborn Vegetation Reserve at Koonamore: Long-term observations of changes in arid vegetation. In: "Rangelands, a Resource under Siege." Proc. 2nd Internat. Rangelands Congress. Aust. Acad. Science, Canberra, pp67-8.
- Sinclair, R. (1996) Mulga regeneration at Koonamore. in Conference Papers, The Australian Rangeland Society 9th Biennial Conference, eds L.P. Hunt and R. Sinclair. Australian Rangeland Society, Port Augusta, South Australia, pp255-256.
- Sinclair, R. (1999) Koonamore: The T.G.B. Osborn Vegetation Reserve. *Biology Society of South Australia*, Issue 3, March 1999. pp 4-6.

Publications based on work at the TGB Osborn Vegetation Reserve

- Sinclair, R. (2002) Dead Wood in the Arid Zone; Some data from the TGB Osborn Vegetation Reserve, Koonamore. In "Shifting Camp", Conference Proceedings, Australian Rangelands Society 12th Biennial Conference, eds Sarah Nicolson & David Wilcox, Kalgoorlie Sept. 2002. pp 123 - 128.
- Sinclair, R. (2004) Persistence of dead trees and fallen timber in the arid zone: 76 years of data from the T.G.B. Osborn Vegetation Reserve, Koonamore, South Australia. *Rangeland Journal* 26(1): 111-22.
- Sinclair, R. (2005) Long-term changes in vegetation, gradual and episodic, on the TGB Osborn Vegetation Reserve, Koonamore, South Australia, 1926-2002. *Australian Journal of Botany*, 53: 283-296.
- Sinclair, R. and Facelli, J.M. (2019) Ninety years of change on the TGB Osborn Vegetation Reserve, Koonamore: a unique research opportunity. *Rangel. J.* 41, 185.
- Sinclair, R. and Thomas, D.A. (1970) Optical properties of leaves of some species in arid South Australia. *Aust. J. Bot.* 18: 261-273.
- Sinclair, R., Emmerson, L.M., and Ladd, D. R. (1995) The T.G.B. Osborn Vegetation Reserve, Koonamore, South Australia. 70 years of vegetation monitoring. Poster displayed at the Ecological Society of America, Annual Meeting, Utah, USA.
- Sinclair, R. (1984) The T.G.B. Osborn Reserve; Koonamore. *Aust. Rangel. Soc., Range Management Newsletter* 84/4.
- Specht, R.L. (1972) The Vegetation of South Australia. The Flora and Fauna of South Australia Handbooks Committee. Second Edition. Govt Printer, Adelaide, 328 pp.
- Specht, R.L. and Specht, A. (2002) Australian Plant Communities: dynamics of structure, growth and biodiversity. Oxford University Press, 2nd Edition, Melbourne, 492pp.
- Walker, C.N. and Sinclair, R. (1992) Soil salinity is correlated with a decline in $\delta^{13}C$ discrimination in leaves of *Atriplex* species. *Australian Journal of Ecology* 17: 83-88.
- Wood, J.G. (1936) Regeneration of the vegetation on the Koonamore Vegetation Reserve, 1926 to 1936. *Trans. Roy. Soc. S. Aust.* 60: 96-111.

Theses, The University of Adelaide

- Carrodus, B.B. (1962) Some aspects of the Ecology of arid South Australia. Masters thesis, Univ. of Adelaide.
- Coleman, D.F. (1982) The Carbon balance of *Atriplex vesicaria*. PhD Thesis, Univ. of Adelaide.
- Cox, J.A. (1982) Drought tolerance and reproductive strategy of two arid zone annuals, *Erodium cicutarium* and *Erodium crinitum* (Geraniaceae) Hons Thesis, Botany Dept., Univ. of Adelaide.
- Crisp, M.D. (1975) Long term change in arid zone vegetation at Koonamore, South Australia. PhD Thesis, Univ. of Adelaide.
- Emmerson, L. M. (1999) Persistence mechanisms of *Erodiophyllum elderi*, an arid land daisy with a patchy distribution. PhD Thesis, Univ. of Adelaide.
- Hastwell, G.T. (2001) Facilitation and Fertile Islands: linking canopy effects with plant interactions. PhD Thesis, Univ. of Adelaide.
- Rogers, R.W. (1970) Ecology of soil-surface lichens in arid south-eastern Australia. PhD Thesis, Univ. of Adelaide.
- Sinclair, R. (1967) Some aspects of the energy balance of arid zone plants. PhD Thesis, Univ. of Adelaide.
- West, L. J. (1997) Age structure and population studies on two subspecies of *Senna artemesioides* (Desert Cassia, Puntly Bush) on Koonamore Station, South Australia. Honours thesis, Botany Dept., Univ. of Adelaide.